

Motivations	Wanting to have fun Wanting to try out computer coding Wanting to learn new technologies Wanting to meet new people Wanting to share my experiences with others Wanting to see what others are working on Wanting to do better in school Wanting to advance my career
Mentoring experience	My mentor was patient. My mentor guided me to find solutions. My mentor solved my technical problems. The mentor and students ratio was insufficient My mentor answered my question in a clear way
Handout	The handout helped improve my productivity The handout was hard to understand
Kick-off event	The kick-off event helped improve my productivity The kick-off event helped improve my effectiveness

TABLE I: Themes extracted from the first survey.